

Basilica of Saint Epiphianos

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Entry tags: Christian, Early Christianity, Religious Group, Christian Orthodox, Cyprus, Classical Indo-European, Indo-European, Language, Salamis, Religious Place, Graeco-Phrygian, Greek

Built in the late 4th or the early 5th century, the Basilica of Saint Epiphianos is located in ancient Salamis, 8 km north of the city of Famagusta (Ammochostos in Greek), on the east coast of the island of Cyprus. The Basilica is currently in a ruinous state. It was founded by Saint Epiphianos, Bishop of Constantia, precisely during the last years of his episcopacy (367-403), but it was completed by his successor, Savinos. Although currently the monument it is known under the name of its founder, who was buried therein, there is no evidence regarding its original dedication. The timber-roofed, seven-aisled basilica with the tripartite sanctuary replaced a smaller church. The basilica included in the east also a baptistery with a cruciform baptismal font and a hypocaust system for warming the water, a complex of halls (east), a narthex terminating into a semi-circular inscribed apse and an atrium (not yet excavated), while the north and south sides of the nave had adjunct narrow corridors running parallel to them, communicating with them via doors and possibly windows as well. These were believed to have been the areas used by those who were not baptized (katechoumena). In the 6th century, following an earthquake, the basilica was repaired, becoming at this phase a five-aisled building. The Life of Saint Epiphianos mentions that he was buried on the right side of the basilica, with the permission of Emperor Arcadius, despite the fact that the building was not yet finished. This was confirmed by the excavated tomb at the eastern part of the second south aisle, lined with marble. Following the Arab raids of the 7th century, the basilica was rebuilt and so the tomb of the Saint was incorporated into the narthex of the new building. However, only part of his relics remained in the basilica, which continued to be an important centre of pilgrimage up to the 14th century. His relics were later transferred to the church of Saint Symeon in the nearby city of Famagusta. The second timber-roofed basilica with the synthronon, of much smaller dimensions, was erected to the east of the south aisles of the first basilica, probably between 653 and 690. The second timber-roofed basilica was replaced in the 8th century by a three-aisled, barrel-vaulted church carrying three domes on the central axis. This was the first example of a church belonging to the type of the multi-domed churches encountered in Cyprus. During the Lusignan period side apses were added to the church, while the tomb of Saint Epiphianos was also repaired. The monument was last repaired in the 16th century. Following the first trial excavation of 1890 by the Archaeological Expedition of the British Museum, excavations were undertaken through the 20th century. In 1926 was excavated the nave, under the direction of George Jeffery. Andreas Dikigoropoulos has led the excavations which have taken place during the period 1954-1959.

Date Range: 370 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Basilica of Saint Epiphianos

Region tags: Salamis, Cyprus

Basilica of Saint Epiphianos, Salamis, Cyprus

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Foulías, A. “The Basilica of Saint Epiphánios: Architecture and Chronology.” In *Salamis of Cyprus History and Archaeology from the Earliest Times to Late Antiquity*. Conference in Nicosia, 21-23 May 2015, edited by C. Ioannou, T. Mavrojannis, and S. Rogge. Münster, 2019.
- Source 2: Papageorgíou, A. “Η Βασιλική Του Αγίου Επιφανίου.” *Επετηρίδα Κέντρου Μελετών Ιεράς Μονής Κύκκου* 8 (2008).
- Source 3: Foulías, A. “Βασιλική (Σαλαμίνα).” In *Μεγάλη Χριστιανική Ορθόδοξη Εγκυκλοπαίδεια*. Athens, 2012.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://ibcc.dighum.kcl.ac.uk/entries/b0037.html>
- Source 1 Description: Description of the Basilica of Saint Epiphánios, Inventory of Byzantine Churches on Cyprus

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

- Scientific

Years of excavation:

- Year range: 1890, 1926, 1954-1959

Name of excavation

- Official or descriptive name: Excavations of the Basilica of Salamis

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Body of water (as distinct from source)

Notes: The Basilica of Saint Epiphánios is located on the east coast of the island of Cyprus

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Notes: The Basilica is built in the site of Salamis

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Notes: The area is actually an archaeological site. However, when it was built it was indeed situated in an urbanized area, i.e. Salamis

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Notes: The area is actually an archaeological site. However, when it was built it was indeed situated in an urbanized area, i.e. Salamis

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: The area is actually an archaeological site. However, when it was built it was indeed situated in an urbanized area, i.e. Salamis

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: The basilica is located on the east coast of the island of Cyprus

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: The monument was originally a basilica, which has replaced a smaller church. A second basilica was built on the same site. A three-aisled, barrel-vaulted church carrying three domes on the central axis replaced the latter.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

–Other [specify]: The monument was originally a basilica, which has replaced a smaller church. A second basilica was built on the same site, after the Arab raids. A three-aisled, barrel-vaulted church carrying three domes on the central axis replaced the latter.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–As the result of war

–Other [specify]: The monument was originally a basilica, which has replaced a smaller church. A second basilica was built on the same site, after the Arab raids. A three-aisled, barrel-vaulted church carrying three domes on the central axis replaced the latter.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

–Other [specify]: The monument was originally a basilica, which has replaced a smaller church. A second basilica was built on the same site, after the Arab raids. A three-aisled, barrel-vaulted church carrying three domes on the central axis replaced the latter.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The basilica was reconstructed/repared quite a few times

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is most probable that the churches built on the site were sponsored by an external financial/material donation

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

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↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Sand
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

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↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The basilica is in a ruinous state. Moreover it was not excavated, so we do not possess all the necessary evidence regarding the materials used during all the phases

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: The place is a basilica. However, Saint Epiphanius, bishop of Constantia and founder of the basilica was buried therein

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Notes: The tomb of Saint Epiphanius is currently a cenotaph, since his relics were moved out of the basilica

In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The basilica was founded by Saint Epiphanius. He was buried in the monument but later when the monument was destroyed his relics were moved to other places. The tomb of the Saint is still visible though

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Notes: The basilica is in ruins and so services are not being performed there

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Notes: The basilica was only partially excavated and so only some remains are still visible

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: Pilgrims can however visit the basilica, although the monument is in ruins

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Notes: The basilica is in ruins and so it is not inhabited

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The Department of Antiquities of Cyprus was in charge prior to the Turkish invasion of 1974. Since then the site of Salamis can be visited but the basilica was not excavated or restored in any way

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Notes: There are no scriptures associated with the basilica per se. However, Saint Epiphanius bishop of Salamis, who founded the basilica, was a prolific writer

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Basilica of Saint Epiphanius, Des Gagniers, J. , and T. T. Tinh. Dix Campagnes De Fouilles(1964–1974), Vol. 1: Introduction Historique. La Basilique. Sainte-Foy, 1985.

Reference: Basilica of Saint Epiphanius, Foulis, A.. “Βασιλική (Σαλαμίνα)”. In Μεγάλη Χριστιανική Ορθόδοξη Εγκυκλοπαίδεια, 257–58. Athens, 2012.

Reference: Basilica of Saint Epiphanius, Jeffery, G.. “The Basilica of Constantia Cyprus”. Antiquaries Journal, no. 8 (1928).

Reference: Basilica of Saint Eriphanios, Παπαγεωργίου, Α.. “Η Βασιλική Του Αγίου Επιφανίου”. Επετηρίδα Κέντρου Μελετών Ιεράς Μονής Κύκκου 8 (2008).

Reference: Basilica of Saint Eriphanios, Foulías, Α.. “The Basilica of Saint Eriphanios: Architecture and Chronology”. In *Salamis of Cyprus History and Archaeology from the Earliest Times to Late Antiquity*. Conference in Nicosia, 21-23 May 2015, edited by C. Ioannou, T. Mavrojannis, and S. Rogge. Münster, 2019.